

EFFECTIVENESS OF LIQUID ORGANIC FERTILIZER AND MYCORRHIZA FUNGI TO *FICUS L.* GROWTH IN CONSERVATION FORESTS

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Microbiology is a branch of biological sciences that studies microorganisms. The object of the study is usually all creatures that need to be seen with a microscope, especially bacteria, fungi, microscopic algae, protozoa, and Archaea. The development of bacterial culture media plays a very important role in the field of microbiology. By isolating a bacteria and growing it with artificial media can identify, and study the nature of a bacteria. Waluyo (2009) said that microbiology is widely developed in various fields of science, such as agriculture, industry, health, environment, food, even space. The study of plant physiology is another branch of biological sciences about all internal plant activities, chemical and physical processes related to plant life, with its scope of cells and cell organelles, particle movement in the form of diffusion, osmosis and imbibisi. Then the study of plant ecology is a science that studies the reciprocal relationship between plants and their environment, this study also examines all environmental factors that affect the existence of one plant species (species ecology), or one plant community (community ecology) in a particular area. From the merger of the study is expected to support the birth of scientific innovation in the field of organic waste utilization and in the field of conservation *Ficus L.*

Garbage is a serious problem faced by a city, because landfills can cause air, water and soil pollution that causes aesthetic and health problems (Sinaga, 2009). According to Wibowo and Djajawinata (2002) of the total city waste produced, about 53.3% were not handled properly. Purwasasmita (1989) reported that about 70–80% of the city's waste is organic. Thus, there needs to be proper handling so that the city's organic waste can be reduced. One way that can be done is to reuse the city's organic waste as raw materials for liquid organic fertilizer (POC). Liquid organic fertilizer contains macro and micro essential nutrients. This fertilizer is generally applied through leaves or called foliar liquid fertilizer. Basically POC raw materials can come from all organic materials. According to Hadisuwito (2007) POC raw materials are very good wet organic materials or organic materials that have a high water content such as the rest of fruits and vegetable remains. Broadly speaking the advantages of the utilization of liquid organic fertilizers are improvements in physical, chemical and biological properties of soil as well as social conditions (Bunyamin, 2008). Eka, et al (2017) said that the administration of POC can increase the availability of nutrients needed for the formation of chlorophyll, such as N, C, H, O and Mg.

The provision of organic fertilizer can increase the activity of soil microbes both microflora and microfauna (Farida, 1995). This is because organic fertilizer is able to increase the nutrient content in the soil so that with good soil conditions can stimulate the activity of soil microbes. Mycorrhiza is one of the groups of microorganisms that play a role in helping the absorption of nutrients by plants. Mycorrhiza is a structure formed due to symbiosis mutualism

between soil fungi and plant roots (Subiksa, 2002). The existence of mutualistic symbiosis between mycorrhiza fungi and plant rooting can help plant growth to be better. In Feby's research, et al (2016) stated that, the administration of compost fertilizer by inoculating several doses of mycorrhiza fungi on the soil media ultisol gives a real influence on the increase in diameter of surian seedling stems but gives no real difference in the height and number of leaves. According to Akhyar, et al (2015) the average dry weight of stems, leaves and roots is higher at a dose of 10 g of mycorrhiza fungi compared to other doses.

The use of liquid organic fertilizer with the addition of a dose of mycorrhiza fungi is expected to support the growth of plant seeds in conservation areas such as *Ficus. L. Ficus* is one of the most important plant species of forest ecosystems. Some of the living organisms depend on the presence of *Ficus*, such as insects of a specific nature (Whitmore, 1978). *Ficus* consists of nearly 800 species, spread throughout the world, but more commonly found in the tropics and mostly in Indo-Malesia (Ridley, 1925). Of the many types of *Ficus*, Ridley (1925) reported there were 92 species in Asia and tropical Asia. Therefore, it is necessary to maintain its existence, moreover, some companies deliberately set aside conservation forests as a source and reserve of water for plantation communities and surrounding areas. According to Nur'aini (2013) *Ficus* types were found to be at varying heights. The types of *Ficus* found are at an altitude of 300-543 meters above sea level, Generally *Ficus* is found in lowland areas, but six of them are in the highland areas namely *F. benjamina*, *F. callosa*, *F. grassularioides* *F. uniglandulosa*, and *F. xylophylla* and the distinguishing character of the types of *Ficus* obtained can be seen in variations habit, stipula, leaf morphology, waxy gland , and fruit.

From the above exposure, good processing for organic waste in urban areas is to process it into liquid organic fertilizer (POC) with the help of microbiology studies to study the nature of a mycoorganism contained in it and with the addition of fungi mycorrhiza can help the absorption of liquid organic fertilizer nutrients in the form of macro nutrients and essential microbes by utilizing plant physiology studies to see the internal activity of plants given POC and fungi micoriza doses. The administration of POC and the dose of mycorrhiza fungi is expected to support the growth of plant seeds in conservation areas based on plant ecology study data stating that *Ficus. L* is one of the conservation area plants that need to be maintained its existence. The linkage between the study of microbiology, plant physiology and plant ecology, is expected to give birth to scientific innovations in the field of organic waste utilization and in the field of conservation *Ficus L*.

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